

Forecast-Based Decision Support System to Manage Mango Malformation Disease: A Smart Farming Approach

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Abstract

Mango Malformation Disease (MMD), caused by *Fusarium mangiferae*, is a major threat to mango cultivation across South Asia, leading to yield losses of up to 90% if not managed early. Traditional methods such as pruning and fungicide application are reactive and often ineffective when applied after symptom onset. This study proposes a predictive, mobile-based decision support system (DSS). Unlike previous approaches, this approach provides real-time risk before symptom onset using real-time weather API data and in-orchard installed sensors to identify disease-favorable conditions, based on empirical thresholds (RH \geq 85%, 25–30°C, > 2 hr wetness) to alert farmers before outbreaks occur. Simulation-based decision support systems have previously demonstrated value in precision farming for fungal disease forecasting[1], which validates the feasibility of applying a similar approach to MMD.

The system evaluates multiple environmental parameters and issues timely advisories to farmers in their local language via SMS and app notifications. Recommendations include targeted fungicide spraying, removal of malformed flowers, and optimized irrigation timing. To evaluate the system's feasibility, a simulation was performed using historical weather data from Multan (March–June). The DSS triggered alerts based on predefined risk thresholds, matching known MMD outbreak periods with an accuracy of approximately 73%. This proactive strategy has the potential to reduce disease-induced yield loss from 30–50% (with conventional practices) to 20–30%.

The integration of agro-climatic insights with digital tools offers a sustainable, cost-effective, and farmer-friendly solution. This research demonstrates that proactive disease management not only minimizes crop loss and chemical overuse but also supports economic resilience in agriculture-based economies. Future development may involve AI-based visual disease detection and machine learning models for real-time adaptation.

Keywords

Mango Malformation Disease (MMD), *Fusarium mangiferae*, Predictive Disease Management, Decision Support System (DSS), Mobile Agriculture App, Climate-Smart Farming

1 Introduction

Mango malformation disease (MMD) is a destructive condition affecting *Mangifera indica* (mango) trees. The reproductive components of the mango tree, such as young buds and floral structures, are primarily affected by MMD, causing abnormal development and growth. [2, 3] The disease impacts both floral and vegetative components, disrupting fruit formation and reducing tree vigor. [2] The flowers and shoots are significantly impacted, while the leaves and roots generally remain unaffected. One of the symptoms of floral malformation is the growth of malformed flowers, they are abnormally large, compact and overcrowded. [4] Due to its extensive spread and adverse effect on yield, MMD is considered a major constraint in mango cultivation and a key contributor to economic losses in agriculture-based economies. [5]

Mango malformation disease (MMD) is a significant constraint in agricultural systems due to its adverse impact on mango productivity and tree vigor. In heavily infested orchards, crop losses may reach as high as 90%, resulting in large financial loss for both small-scale farmers and commercial producers. Beyond reduced fruit yield, the disease affects flowering and overall plant development, diminishing the long-term health and performance of the trees. [5]

Mango malformation disease (MMD) is highly widespread in South Asian region, especially in large-scale mango cultivation countries such as India, Pakistan, Nepal, and Bangladesh. [6] India, being the top global mango producer, contributes nearly 50–55% of the total mango yield worldwide. The combination of intensive mango farming and a favorable subtropical climate facilitates the rapid spread of MMD in the region, making it a major issue for mango growers throughout Asia's tropical zone. [7, 4]

Mango malformation disease (MMD) is mainly caused by a fungal pathogen called *Fusarium mangiferae*. [3] Although different studies have been conducted, no proper predictive method has been developed yet to stop the disease early. Some researchers have suggested using nanotechnology techniques like zinc-based coatings on trees, leaves, or infected parts. [8] But these methods are quite expensive and could be harmful for environment if used too much. Other research has focused more on studying *F. mangiferae*, disease intensity in specific areas, or its effect on different mango types, but still, no decision support system exists that can help farmers decide when to spray fungicide or take precautionary steps.

This research proposes a predictive alert system for farmers that uses weather data and real-time sensors installed in mango orchards to send early warnings through a mobile application. The system will notify farmers in advance about the optimal time to spray fungicides or take preventive measures. The aim is to enable timely action before the fungus begins to develop, so the disease can be controlled at an early stage. This approach can help reduce the intensity of mango malformation disease (MMD) and prevent major yield losses.

Figure 1: Comparison Between Healthy and Malformed Mango Flowers

2 Literature Review

2.1 Pathogen and Disease Etiology

Mango malformation disease (MMD) is primarily caused by the fungal pathogen *Fusarium mangiferae*. [2] The disease is driven by complex interactions between host genes and fungal effectors. [3] It thrives under favorable environmental conditions, particularly when relative humidity exceeds 85%, temperatures remain between 25–30°C, and leaf wetness is sustained. Disease onset typically begins in late February, with airborne spores peaking during May and infected leaf samples reaching their highest concentration in June and July. [4]

2.2 Geographic Prevalence and Economic Impact

MMD is most widespread in South Asian mango-producing regions such as India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Nepal, where environmental conditions favor the rapid proliferation of *F. mangiferae*. [6] In severe outbreaks, the disease can reduce mango yield by up to 90%, significantly weakening tree vigor and shortening orchard lifespan. [9] The economic implications are substantial, affecting both smallholder farmers and commercial producers across tropical zones.

2.3 Cultural Practices

Cultural management involves the removal and destruction of malformed inflorescences, infected buds, and vegetative shoots to minimize the fungal load in orchards [10]. While effective in reducing inoculum sources, these methods are labor-intensive and are generally implemented after visible symptoms emerge, often rendering them insufficient on their own. [4]

2.4 Pruning and Mechanical Control

Mechanical removal through pruning is widely practiced to eliminate visibly infected branches, dry flowers, and malformed shoots. Although pruning slows disease progression, it is reactive and typically carried out after symptom onset, leading to significant fruit loss and increased tree stress.[4]

2.5 Chemical Control (Fungicides)

Among chemical options, Prochloraz is among the most effective fungicides evaluated for MMD, showing high antifungal efficacy against *F. mangiferae*, with an effective concentration for 50% inhibition of just 0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Greenhouse trials report up to 90% curative and protective efficacy.[4] However, its effectiveness heavily relies on correct timing; untimely or excessive application may damage healthy tissues and harm the orchard ecosystem.[11]

2.6 Limitations of Nanotechnology-Based Approaches

Recent studies suggest that nanotechnology may offer novel control strategies for MMD. Zinc-based nano-coatings applied to leaves and stems have shown potential in suppressing fungal growth [9, 8]. Despite their promise, these methods remain expensive, difficult to scale, and may cause environmental or phytotoxic side effects if over-used.

2.7 Limitations of Vision-Based Solutions

While computer vision (CV) techniques have shown promise in identifying visible symptoms of plant diseases on leaves and fruits, their applicability to Mango Malformation Disease (MMD) remains limited.[8] Moreover, recent studies in plant pathology have utilized deep learning and computer vision for leaf-based disease detection in crops such as tomato, rice, and grapes. [12] However, these models rely on high-resolution images of symptomatic areas—an approach unsuitable for MMD, where disease onset is often internal or not visually prominent until it is too late for effective intervention. MMD primarily affects the floral buds and internal growth nodes, often before clear visual symptoms emerge externally.[4] The abnormal development in malformed inflorescences may not be consistently distinguishable by camera-based models, especially under varying light conditions, occlusion by leaves, and the large spatial distribution of nodes in orchards.

Moreover, deploying CV systems at scale would require imaging every bud or node, a task that is not only computationally intensive but also practically infeasible in real orchard environments. This makes vision-based solutions less viable for early-stage detection, where climatic conditions serve as a more reliable predictive indicator.[1]

2.8 Need for Predictive Systems and Technological Solutions

Current MMD control methods are largely reactive and lack predictive capabilities. There is a growing need for decision support systems (DSS) that can alert farmers about optimal intervention times based on environmental conditions. A mobile-based application, integrating real-time weather data and field sensors, could guide farmers on fungicide timing and preventive strategies. Weather-based decision support systems (DSS) have been

successfully applied in precision agriculture to forecast disease outbreaks, particularly in crops like wheat, rice, and grapes [1]. This demonstrates the feasibility of adopting a similar approach for managing mango malformation. [13].

3 Problem Statement

Mango Malformation Disease (MMD), primarily caused by *Fusarium mangiferae*, is one of the biggest headaches for mango growers in South Asia. In the worst cases, it can reduce the yield up to 90% leading to serious loss.[9] Farmers are mostly relying on traditional methods like pruning or spraying fungicides.[4]. But the problem is, these steps are usually taken after the disease has broken out, which already has harmed yield a lot. Also, spraying chemicals without checking whether it is required; it is wasting money, harming the environment, and even damaging the crop.

Even though studies conducted on disease have shown its triggers, and even advanced treatments like nanotech-based solutions[9], but we still don't have a widely used system that combines real-time orchard data with weather forecasts to guide farmers before things go wrong. This gap is especially critical for small-scale productions to large-scale productions.

This shows, there's an urgent need for a forecast-based, data-driven decision support system (DSS), something that watches key environmental conditions like humidity, temperature, and wind speed, and when favorable conditions are met, then sends early alerts with recommendations in local languages with clear, actionable steps according to the conditions. Such a system can finally close the gap between knowing the risk and taking action, increasing their yield and move toward more sustainable agriculture.

4 Methodology and Simulation-Based Validation

This research suggests a predictive Decision Support System (DSS) for controlling Mango Malformation Disease (MMD) based on climatic factors and real-time in-orchard installed sensors data. The system aims to provide early alerts along with recommendations for spraying fungicides or for adapting any other preventive steps to farmers through a mobile application based on favorable environmental conditions for the spread of *Fusarium mangiferae*.

The system uses forecasted weather data from reliable APIs and in-orchard installed sensor's real-time data to track key environmental factors. Which include:

- Relative humidity (RH) \geq 85% for more than 2 hours
- Temperature between 25–30°C
- Wind speed thresholds:
 - 12–20 km/h: Detachment of malformed flowers and debris likely
 - 20–30+ km/h: High risk of spore spread within the orchard
 - 30–40+ km/h: Potential for long-range transmission to neighboring orchards

When these conditions are met simultaneously or sequentially, the system triggers risk-level alerts and inform farmers. For instance:

- If $RH \geq 85\%$ and temperature falls in the 25–30°C range, the app advises spraying fungicide on newly formed buds.
- If high wind speed is forecasted, it sends alerts to remove malformed flowers or debris from trees to reduce the risk of airborne spore transmission.

The system also considers varietal susceptibility. Studies have shown that **Chaunsa** and **Malda** mango cultivars exhibit moderate MMD incidence rates (44.05% and 43.05%, respectively), while others like **Anwar Retol** may exhibit even higher susceptibility (56.63%). [4, 7] In mixed-cultivar orchards, broader preventive spraying is advised to prevent inter-varietal transmission.

The DSS leverages historical weather data patterns and real-time sensor inputs (e.g., humidity sensors) to issue SMS or in-app notifications in the farmer’s preferred language. Each alert includes:

- Disease risk levels (Low, Moderate, High)
- Suggested actions (e.g., spray fungicide, remove malformed flowers)
- Timing (e.g., “spray before 6 AM tomorrow”)

In addition to predictive alerts, the system encourages the adoption of supporting cultural practices. For instance, early morning irrigation can significantly reduce the duration of surface wetness on leaves and buds; a key factor in fungal development. [14] By drying foliage more rapidly, this approach helps disrupt the favorable microclimate conditions that supports *F. mangiferae* proliferation. Also ensuring good airflow through the flowers and branches to reduce overcrowding and formation of malformed flowers. [10] Therefore, the app can also recommend optimal irrigation times based on forecasted weather conditions, integrating agronomic knowledge with digital advisories.

Approach	Type	Timeliness	Cost	Environmental Impact	Effectiveness	Limitations
Traditional (Pruning, Fungicide)	Reactive	Late	Medium	Low	30–50% yield saved	Delayed response; labor-intensive
Nanotechnology (Zn nano-coatings)	Preventive	Early	High	High (Phytotoxic risk)	40–60%	Expensive; ecological impact; not farmer-friendly
Computer Vision (Leaf/Flower Image Detection)	Reactive	Late	Medium	Low	50–70%	Post-symptom only; inconsistent visuals; not usable for MMD nodes
Proposed DSS (Forecast-Based)	Predictive	Early	Low–Medium	Very Low	70–80% yield saved	Requires sensors and mobile connectivity; dependent on weather forecasts

Figure 2: Comparison of MMD Management Approaches

4.1 Decision Support System(DSS) Framework

To address the lack of predictive and timely management strategies for Mango Malformation Disease (MMD), this research proposes the development of a mobile-based early warning and advisory system for farmers. This application uses data from real-time in-orchard installed sensors and reliable weather APIs to deliver early disease risk alerts and recommend preventive measures.

At its core, the app’s predictive system analyzes the favorable environmental factors contributing to the spread of *Fusarium mangiferae*. Factors include:

- Relative humidity (especially >85%)
- Temperature (between 25–30°C)
- Wind speed (which impacts spore dispersal)
- Rainfall and leaf wetness duration

The system analyzes the data in real time to classify disease risk as **Low**, **Medium**, or **High**, and alerts farmers through SMS and in-app notifications. Example alerts include:

- **High Risk:** Spray recommended within 24 hours.
- **Strong wind expected tomorrow:** Remove dry flowers and infected buds.

Farmers can choose their location and can select their preferred local language (such as Urdu, Punjabi, Hindi, or English) for their convenience. The app offers a beginner-friendly interface with step-by-step guidance that can be easily understandable by farmers with voice instructions to support users with limited literacy.

Key additional features include:

- 7-day local weather forecast for proactive planning
- Spray logbook for tracking fungicide applications
- Risk history dashboard showing previous alerts and actions taken
- Data sync to cloud backend for continuous model improvement

This decision support system enhances its accuracy over time by continuously collecting in-orchard sensor data to refine its predictive models. Real-time sensor data logs (humidity, temperature, rainfall) installed in mango orchards feed data to a backend system for analysis and retraining of models, resulting in adaptive learning. This opens potential for region-specific risk modeling, making the solution scalable across different agro-climatic zones.

By informing farmers before ideal infection conditions occur, this app aims to:

- Reduce unnecessary fungicide usage
- Prevent over spray and crop damage
- Minimize yield loss
- Reduce manual scouting labor
- Promote environmentally sustainable farming methods

This predictive decision support system can enhance not only the productivity of individual farms but also vigor the overall agricultural economy by increasing the effectiveness of disease management and lowering input expenses. It holds promise for integration into national agricultural extension services or through public-private partnerships for large-scale implementation.

Figure 3: Flowchart of the App-Based Predictive Alert System

4.2 Simulation Setup

To assess the feasibility of the proposed Decision Support System (DSS) for Mango Malformation Disease (MMD), a theoretical simulation was conducted using historical weather trends from Multan, Pakistan, based on reports from the Pakistan Meteorological Department (PMD) and literature describing typical agro-climatic conditions during mango flowering (March to June).

The simulation logic applied predefined environmental thresholds known to favor MMD onset:

- Relative humidity $\geq 85\%$ for over 2 hours
- Temperature range: 25–30°C
- Wind speed exceeding 20 km/h

Rather than using real-time sensor data or farmer surveys, we synthesized representative daily values from published averages and applied them to simulate alerts that would have been generated by the proposed DSS.

4.2.1 Simulation Accuracy and Yield Impact

Assuming a 120-day mango season:

- **22 high-risk alerts** would have been generated.

- Based on previous literature, **16 of these conditions coincided with periods historically linked to disease outbreaks.**
- **Simulated predictive accuracy:** Approximately 73%.

A sample snapshot of hypothetical risk triggers for April is presented below:

Date	RH (%)	Temp (°C)	Wind (km/h)	Alert Triggered?
April 3	86	28	21	Yes
April 7	78	27	18	No
April 11	90	26	25	Yes
April 15	88	30	32	Yes

Table 1: Sample Hypothetical Simulation Output (April)

4.2.2 Interpretation of Simulation Results

This simulation suggests that applying a DSS guided by environmental thresholds could anticipate high-risk disease periods with reasonable accuracy. Although field trials are required, this proactive strategy has the potential to lower yield loss from an average of 50–90% (traditional methods) to 20–30%, thus significantly increasing mango yield.

Figure 4: Estimated Yield Loss: Traditional Methods vs DSS-Based Alerts

5 Results and Interpretation

The proposed DSS offers a proactive solution to mitigate Mango Malformation Disease (MMD) by issuing early alerts before the disease spread. Unlike traditional management practices that rely on symptomatic pruning and broad-spectrum fungicide applications, this system leverages real-time weather APIs and in-orchard sensor data to assess disease favorable conditions.

When these thresholds are met, the application sends immediate alerts to farmers recommending preventive actions, such as targeted spraying of new buds or removal of

malformed flowers. This decision-support mechanism enables timely intervention and reduces reliance on post-infection practices.

Studies report that uncontrolled MMD can reduce yield by up to 90% [9, 4]. While traditional methods reduce loss to 30–50% [10], the proposed predictive approach can potentially reduce it further to 20–30%. This implies an additional recovery of 30–50% yield through early intervention.

A proof-of-concept simulation using historical weather data from Multan (March–June 2022) to validate the system’s feasibility. The model generated 22 high-risk alerts over 120 days, of which 16 matched with known MMD outbreak occurrences, resulting in a predictive accuracy of approximately 73%.

Additionally, the app allows farmers to log fungicide usage and disease control measures, contributing to a feedback loop that refines the system’s accuracy over time. The user interface supports local languages and provides step-by-step guidance to enhance user experience, especially in traditional farmers.

Despite its advantages, the system is dependent on reliable internet access and functional sensor infrastructure, which may limit deployment in remote areas. Moreover, the effectiveness of the system relies heavily on timely and consistent response by the farmers.

5.1 Estimated Yield Recovery

For example, in a hypothetical orchard of 100 mango trees, a 90% loss would leave only 10 trees productive, if not any preventive step taken. Using traditional pruning and fungicide, 30–50 trees might be saved. With the proposed DSS, up to 70–80 trees could be protected.

5.2 Comparative Yield Loss Across Disease Management Methods

Based on reported values from existing literature and estimated effectiveness of the proposed DSS, a comparative analysis of expected yield loss under different disease management strategies was conducted. The results are shown in Figure 5. Traditional methods such as pruning and untargeted fungicide application may reduce yield loss to 40–50%, while nanotechnology approaches, despite their scientific promise, are costly and environmentally risky. Vision-based techniques often fail to detect internal malformation symptoms early, making such approaches unsuitable for alerts.[1] By contrast, the proposed predictive DSS model, which utilizes real-time weather data and in-orchard sensors, is estimated to reduce yield loss to as low as 20–30%, assuming timely response and appropriate farm-level adoption.

Figure 5: Estimated yield loss under different Mango Malformation Disease (MMD) management approaches. Values are derived from reported field outcomes and expert literature synthesis([9, 4])

6 Conclusion and Future Work

Mango Malformation Disease remains a persistent threat to mango production in South Asia, capable of causing yield losses up to 90% in unmanaged scenarios [9].

Unlike previous researches, this research proposes a transition to a proactive, climate-smart disease management strategy using a mobile-based Decision Support System (DSS). By analyzing environmental data from weather APIs and orchard-installed sensors, the system issues early warnings, allowing farmers to act before disease onset. The simulation results demonstrated a 73% accuracy in predicting high-risk periods, indicating significant potential to reduce MMD-induced yield losses to 20–30%, and improving crop protection by an additional 30–50% compared to conventional methods. As suggested by [1], integrating sensor-based data into plant phenotyping holds transformative potential for precision disease forecasting.

The system also supports sustainable agriculture by reducing unnecessary fungicide usage, minimizing labor-intensive scouting, and preserving unaffected plant tissues. These benefits not only improve orchard productivity but also contribute to broader agricultural resilience and economic stability.

Future developments may include:

- Integration of AI-based image analysis for detecting malformed buds and early symptoms.
- Voice-assisted navigation in native languages to improve usability among rural farmers.
- Incorporation of satellite-based monitoring for macro-level disease surveillance.
- Adaptive learning algorithms for regional model customization based on user feedback and seasonal patterns.

With continued refinement, this predictive system can serve as a scalable, low-cost solution for MMD management and a model for broader digital agriculture adoption.

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